

An Agile Methodology Approach to an Asset Management System for Company A

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ABSTRACT

The researchers discovered that Company A is experiencing challenges in managing and tracking their furniture, appliances, and IT resources. The company currently uses MS Excel as their asset management; however, it became inefficient enough to be used in their business operations anymore ever since the company is growing and gaining more clients. The researchers implemented an Agile Methodology approach in developing the Resource Allocation Management System (RAMS). The Agile Methodology approach allows the developers to divide a big project into smaller and manageable tasks while keeping a close collaboration with the stakeholders for its business processes, progress, and improvement. The researchers would provide a system that keeps track of the whole life cycle of the asset (item specifications, procurement, current user and location, and usage history) where every asset record is protected. The researchers did a total of 11 sprints in creating the system because there are many features that the developers needed to create since the company did not have an efficient asset management system. After development, the researchers would meet with the client again for validation and feedback. In conclusion, the researchers found that the Agile approach was effective in identifying issues and designing solutions that tailor-fit to the business of the client.

KEYWORDS (3 to 5 only)

Asset management, Agile, Asset, Resources

1 INTRODUCTION

Company A was founded in 2011 with a mission to provide quality workspaces through its facility leasing and management services and IT solutions for both local and international corporations who wanted to start their business here in the Philippines. The objective of this firm is to let their clients focus on running their core business values while they effectively manage the leased facilities and IT resources of their client.

Based on the researchers first meeting [1] with Company A, they stated that the current issue of the company is about asset management, especially in manually encoding multiple asset details into the MS Excel file. Ever since the company gained more clients, using MS Excel has proven to be challenging for asset tracking purposes. The MS Excel files are being maintained by several people within the organization, but the application itself presents plenty of risks because of human error. All information is immediately being displayed in the perspective of the user and this tends them to make mistakes especially on rows with duplicated data but different ID numberings. In relation to this, there is no value validation whenever an employee updates a record. Once a mistake is made, it will be complicated to trace back and fix the source of the issue because they have to verify each row on where the asset is located and are the specifications still the same. The company has already experienced these situations before, and it took them more time and effort to properly fix those records.

Furthermore, using Excel is not user-friendly enough. A certain department uses multiple MS Excel files in tracking different types of IT assets . Based on their experiences, they decided to do it this way in order to avoid having one master MS Excel file that can be impacted with 1 single mistake; thus, affecting the validity of each thousands of records.

In relation to this, Company A always caters to the needs of their clients urgently where there are days when their clients demand a certain quantity of assets immediately either today or by the following day. When the Excel file is not updated because of the constraints mentioned above, the company was forced to overspend their financial resources - when in fact they have a stock in their inventory room - just to meet the deadlines provided by the clients. Based on their experience, most of the clients are global based BPOs and Call Centers where the resource allocation time is done fast-paced. The dynamics and deadlines are stiff and demanding depending on their needs. There were also instances where Company A had already purchased additional assets not knowing they actually have spare assets that can be readily deployed.

[1] Desktops, laptops, monitors, IP Phones, infrastructure devices, and UPS.

Employees find it a hassle to record the movement of their assets that do not give them the assurance of their data being saved and protected in the long run; thus, there is a high possibility that this asset management will be skipped.

With all the main issues stated, asset management plays a critical role in the business process of Company A in being able to cater all the demands and requirements for their client in terms of facilities and IT resources. The researchers aims to follow the following objectives:

- *To have an accurate and always up-to-date asset records of all company assets ensuring company assets are properly taken care of without losses.*
- *To make information about a particular company asset readily available to selected stakeholders to guide all decision makings with efficiency.*
- *To manage asset allocation and reduce the chances of unnecessary capex purchases.*
- *To promote accountability that will help protect company assets*
- *To help the company in forecasting its budget needed for replacing and upgrading its assets due to wear and tear to support its business operations*
- *To ensure all assets have a unique asset tag and avoid duplicates that could lead to confusion*

2 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

According to Tim Heng [2] Excel or spreadsheets are commonly used in organizations. He denotes that Excel is not the problem for inconsistencies of already outdated data but rather due to risks within the development process. It is noted that within the development process while Excel as a software creates the need of compiling data into the spreadsheet, the lack of identifying key factors such as scope and requirements creates disparities within the same spreadsheets given to multiple members of the organization. He states that for a spreadsheet to be consistent, there is a need of creating a solid framework complete with the design, development and documentation in mind. In his opinion, what should matter at the end of the day is having the organization minimize spreadsheet risk culture, that way the organization can fully utilize the use of Excel for their IT solution.

Noor Shamsudin [3] developed the “School Asset Management System” (SAMS); the purpose of the system is to make the stationary management run smoothly that will be used in primary and secondary schools in Malaysia. The systems that the schools previously used were Microsoft Word and Microsoft Excel where the recording of assets was done manually; thus, leading to an

incomplete and miscalculation of assets. The system proposed by Shamsudin is divided into 2 parts: inventory stationary and modal assets. The SAMS is a web-based system development where HTML, PHP, and JavaScript were used as the programming language, then the system interacts with the database by using the Server Query Language (SQL). In addition, users will be able to access the system via the Intranet, and the behaviour of the SAMS is expected to book the stationeries needed by the staff before taking the items off the counter. Furthermore, it has security elements where only authorized users are allowed to view the stationeries available. An administrator is also involved in the SAMS - its responsibilities are approving the booking requests of asset item/s, register, update, and delete staff records, and adding assets into the records of the system.

Maha Al-Kasasbeh [4] stated in their study that Asset Management systems are usually used to assist industrial practitioners in the following responsibilities: (1) the assessment of the current condition, (2) prediction of the future deterioration, (3) selection of maintenance and repair strategies, (4) condition improvement after a repair, and (5) asset prioritization and fund allocation. Maha Al-Kasasbeh focused on asset management that involves buildings. Building asset management is a highly challenging task since there are many types of buildings with numerous components that have different maintenance needs and requirements. In relation to this, this is also applicable to the current assets of the company because every kind of asset has different specifications that needs to be treated with special care. In this study approach, a lifecycle work breakdown structure (WBS) for the asset management system was developed to provide a unified hierarchy to categorize and organize building assets. The development of an integrated building asset management requires designing a corresponding database schema that represents the various lifecycle phases of the building assets; the relational database schema used in this system is an entity-relationship conceptual data model.

According to the Corporate Finance Institute (CFI) [5], when it comes to asset management, companies need to keep track of its assets, so its stakeholders will know which assets are available to be employed to provide optimal returns. This process makes it easy for organizations to keep track of their assets, whether liquid or fixed assets; firm owners will know where assets are located, how they are being put to use, and whether there have been changes made into them. Although instances like lost, damaged, or stolen assets are also taken note of in the records, but having a strategic asset management plan, the firms owners will be aware of the assets that have been lost and will eliminate them from the records. In managing assets effectively, a firm owner needs to develop a strategic plan. First, the owner needs to take account of all the assets owned and its corresponding details such as total count of assets, where the assets are, the value of each asset, when they were also acquired, and finally the expected life cycles of the assets. The “life-cycle cost” must also be taken into account because this refers to the maintenance expenses, condition and performance modeling, as well as disposal costs. After that, the owner also takes

into account its overall quality, capacity, and role of different services that the asset provides; this will help the owner determine the operating, maintenance, and renewal activities needed to keep the assets in good condition for the client.

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section will discuss the methods and actions taken in developing a web-based system called Resource Allocation Management System (RAMS).

3.1 Research Design

The researchers will be using the Agile Method approach in order for the client to have a more collaborative interaction with the project. As mentioned by Chuidian, et al [6] in their study, the agile methodology entails the researchers to update the client in order to acquire a better understanding of their stakeholders and develop a system that will fill in the needs that the client specified at the end of a sprint; a sprint is a set amount of time (usually 2-3 weeks) that the researchers use to develop a certain part of the system. At the end of a sprint, a meeting is done in order to check if the deliverables are being met as well as showing the client a progress report; this ensures that a working system is in the works and the client is informed of its progresses all throughout its stages.

In addition, these are the following applications that will be used in developing the system are the following:

- Apache NetBeans IDE 12.0
- Apache Tomcat Server 9.0.37
- MySQL Workbench 8.0
- MySQL Server 8.0
- Apache Maven 3.8.5
- Java 11.0.3

On the other hand, these are the other dependencies that are essential in the features of the system:

- javax.activation-api-1.2.0.jar
- javax.mail-api-1.6.2.jar
- jstl-1.2.jar
- jstl-api-1.2.jar
- mysql-connector-java-8.0.28.jar
- tomcat-jsp-api-9.0.59.jar
- jsp-api-2.1.jar
- protobuf-java-3.11.4.jar
- servlet-api-2.5.jar
- tomcat-el-api-9.0.59.jar

- jstl-impl-1.2.jar

3.2 Physical Deployment Layout of the System

Figure 1 shows how the RAMS will be implemented in the site of Company A. Company A currently has 5 buildings located in Luzon, Philippines. Some of their clients reside in those 5 buildings and sometimes Company A employees must go to those locations to attend to their asset needs. In relation to this, Company A employees reside to work from home amid the pandemic.

Figure 1: Physical deployment of the system in 5 company sites.

The system deployment will be placed in a virtual machine hosted within the existing HP server of Company A. It is expected that the system will be used by less than 10 primary end users only and the hardware resources required for this is very minimal, so that it can be accommodated by their existing server. Since this is a web-based system, it will be easily accessible from any of their office computers if it is connected to their local area network. Furthermore, Company A has a wide area network where all their sites are inter-connected to one another via a Site-to-Site

VPN; thus, allowing end users to access it from any office site. If one needs to access it from home, it can be done as well through their existing remote client VPN connection that they are already doing because of the work from home arrangement due to the pandemic situation.

3.3 Entity Relationship Diagram

Figure 2 shows all the entities and attributes that the researchers deemed necessary for data storage and retrieval from the RAMS. These entities are grouped into tables with different attributes as well as primary keys and foreign keys that show connection with other entities.

Figure 2: Entity Relationship Diagram.

3.4 Data Gathering Procedure

To make the asset management system accurate, the data inputs, fields, and attributes of the system will be coming from the company client by utilizing and examining the MS Excel dummy data provided by both the IT and Facilities department. The column fields of their Excel spreadsheet are essential in knowing what are the parameters that need to be included in developing the system.

By basing on their business process in managing their asset records, each main feature (specifically add item, find item, and edit item) will be conducted on a monthly sprint, and at the end of the sprint, the progress will be shown to the client for feedback. In addition, their feedback on the user interface of the system will also be taken note in improving the system through constant meetings and system demonstrations.

The deadline for this system development is expected to be completed in 1 year. In that case, the developers must ensure that it meets the target deadline and deliver an accurate and working system.

3.5 Validation

The testers will be given a form to evaluate that the system built is a good system. According to Au-yeung [7], there are many characteristics of a good software. It has:

- Usability - this is where users should be able to learn and use a system easily;
- Efficiency - achieving maximum productivity with minimum wasted effort;
- Security - the software should not let attackers access unauthorized resources;
- Accuracy - the accuracy of the outputs is good and it outputs the right results for users;
- Robustness - a system is still working after getting invalid inputs/bad data and stressful environmental conditions; and,
- Readability - by understanding the code, the changes can be implemented faster and in a less error-prone way.

The criteria that will be crafted for the survey is based on these good software criterias while including the challenges of the company clients as stated in the Introduction.

The researchers have decided to go for 2 forms of evaluation metrics: the 5-point Likert Scale and the Customer Effort Score (CES). Sauro [8] stated that the Likert Scale is used for expressing the agreements or disagreements on statements for the target product, and users are limited to rate from 1-5 as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Shows what the Likert Scale of 1-5 means in the testing survey.

Likert Score	Legend
1	Strongly Disagree
2	Disagree
3	Neutral/Ok
4	Agree
5	Strongly Agree

The results gathered will be computed by getting the average of the points for each software criteria stated in each of the tester test surveys. After getting the mean of each tester, another average procedure will be conducted to get the overall results. If the score ends up in a range of 1-2, it will be considered unsatisfactory and must be addressed and fixed immediately. If the scores are ranging from 3 to 5 will be considered satisfactory and no changes will be made.

On the other hand, Customer Effort Score is used to see if the RAMS system is able to solve the issues of the client as compared to their existing system. It focuses on evaluating their experiences in using the system if it is easy or difficult for them to use. Pascal [9] quoted that “The authors found that the ease of having your problems resolved was a much better predictor for satisfaction than having expectations exceeded. Improve the customer experience by easifying journey of your customers.” According to Archit [10], to calculate the customer effort score, the client is provided with a scale that ranges from 1-7 in rating their effort experience; the meaning of scales 1-7 can be found on table 2.

Table 2: Shows what the Customer Effort Score of 1-7 means in the testing survey.

CES Score	Legend
1	Strongly Disagree
2	Disagree
3	Somewhat disagree
4	Undecided
5	Somewhat Agree

6	Agree
75	Strongly Agree

The scores 1-4 (Strongly Disagree - Undecided) is associated with negative results whereas the scores 5-7 (Somewhat Agree - Strongly Agree) represents positive results. To calculate the overall CES, this can be done by getting the average of the results from the total number of responses as shown in Figure 3.

$$\text{Customer Effort Score} = \frac{\text{Sum of all Customer Effort Scores}}{\text{Total number of responses}}$$

Figure 3. The formula to be used in calculating the CES

In constructing the survey questions, the objectives mentioned in the Introduction must correlate with the characteristics of a good software.

These are the ff. questions that will be included in the Likert scale:

- **Accuracy**
 - The RAMS can accurately give all the assets I am searching for based on the selected criteria that I am looking for
 - The RAMS can keep track and protect all the information details of every asset
 - The RAMS was able to take note who made the necessary changes in the condition of the asset under the History Notes section
 - The RAMS can give me exactly the whereabouts of every asset
- **Efficiency**
 - The RAMS can make my tasks of recording or retrieving asset information much quicker when compared to using Excel
 - The response time of the RAMS in terms of speed performance of the system is acceptable
- **Usability**
 - The icons, labels, and description are easily understandable
 - The website design is pleasing to the eyes
 - The website is easy to navigate through when I am doing my tasks

- **Security**

- The RAMS can restrict unauthorized access depending on login credentials and access privileges of the user
- The RAMS can restrict the user access in being only able to read/edit asset information that belongs only to his/her assigned department
- The RAMS can control the user access of either being able to read or edit items based on his/her assigned access privilege as dictated by the job role of the employee
- The RAMS can ensure records of an asset is protected and secured from both accidental changes and deliberate changes by unauthorized personnel

In addition, these are the ff. questions that will be included in the Customer Effort Score:

1. The RAMS made it easier for me to track the assets of the company as compared to MS Excel spreadsheets
2. I am able to understand what I am doing in using the system
3. I am able to add new assets in the RAMS system more efficiently
4. I am able to find the needed assets in the RAMS system more efficiently
5. I am able to edit the asset details more efficiently

Since the testing phase requires time and involvement, the testers for this system are 5 randomly selected 4th year BS Information Technology students from the University of Asia & the Pacific and Company A. Both Likert Scale and Customer Effort Score will be placed in a Google Form, and this form will be sent to Company A and the 5 testers. The scores will be based on the experience of these testers in testing the RAMS system. While taking these evaluation metrics into account, they target the features of the system that were mentioned in the objectives.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section will discuss the results gathered from the testing phase of the system.

4.1 Client Feedback

To determine what modifications are needed in improving the system, the researchers needed to constantly meet with Company A to present the progresses made with system demonstrations. Meeting schedules were negotiated through Google Mail and Google Calendar, and once the two parties had reached to an agreed schedule, actual meetings were held on Google Meet due to the pandemic situation.

Every feedback given by the company was entertained, clarified, and negotiated; these feedbacks were recorded on a separate document. Furthermore, the researchers resorted to the use of a web application called “Trello” to create issue-tickets based on their feedback in order to keep track

what features needed to be further improved. This web application allows the researchers to also document the scenarios that happened during the system development.

Table 3 provides a summary of the list of features that needed to be added, modified, or removed in the asset management system as negotiated with the client. The ones listed below are considered essential feedback in improving the system.

Table 3. Sprint Client Feedback for the RAMS.

Sprint Client Feedback	
Sprint 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Instead of email, let the user enter the username.
Sprint 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Include the IT Department in the system. ● For the IT Department, the asset ID format must start with “FSIA.” ● For the Facilities Department, the asset ID format must start with “FSIB.” ● The sequential unique numbering of the asset ID must be 5 digits instead of 4 digits.
Sprint 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Asset ID should not be the only field to search for; it must include the fields under the Asset Information table, Status table, Client Allocation table, and Acquisition table.
Sprint 7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Under the usage history, the date returned can only be inputted but not the client usage and date deployed. On the other hand, the client usage and date deployed can be inputted but not the date returned. ● For editing in bulk, the Hardware/Software specs and History notes is not necessary to be included. ● Add the status “Disposed.” ● Do not let the system go to an error page when the client just wants to change the data of the floor field. ● The user must be able to edit many asset records at once. ● The history notes only applies to single-edit assets.

Sprint 8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restrict IT employees from adding and editing assets under the Facilities Department and vice versa.
Sprint 9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Remove the “<i>Client Services Department</i>” and “<i>Finance Department</i>” from the user department when adding a user

4.1 Results

The researchers have gathered the results from the testers who tested the RAMS System. These testers were 5 randomly selected 4th year BS Information Technology students from the University of Asia and the Pacific and a representative from Company A. The researchers have considered that these testers were also developing their systems. In this case, these testers have enough knowledge in evaluating the system in terms of its accuracy, efficiency, usability, and security. The researchers also considered the idea of selecting testers from other courses; however, enough, efficient, and effective feedbacks are crucial in developing the system. Therefore, the researchers have concluded that the 5 selected testers would be able to provide enough feedbacks that would be helpful in the development of the system. Table 4 shows the results of the first part of the test survey and Table 5 shows the results of the second part of the test survey.

Table 4. The Likert Scale Results

	Tester #1	Tester #2	Tester #3	Tester #4	Tester #5	Firm A. Rep	Total
Accuracy	5	4.75	4.25	5	5	4.5	4.75
Efficiency	5	5	4.5	5	5	4	4.75
Usability	5	4.67	3.67	5	5	4.67	4.67
Security	5	4.5	4.5	5	5	5	4.83

Table 5. The Customer Effort Score results.

CES Questions	CES Results
The RAMS made it easier for me to track the company assets as compared to MS Excel spreadsheets	6.83
I am able to understand what I am doing in using the system	6.83
I am able to add new assets in the RAMS system more efficiently	6
I am able to find the needed assets in the RAMS system more efficiently	6.67
I am able to edit the details of the asset more efficiently	5.67

4.3 Analysis of the Results

The total scores per criteria indicates what the testers and the client think of the RAMS system.

For the first part of the test survey, none of the scores have a perfect score of 5 although all attributes reached within a good score range. The attribute that scored the highest is Security since it gives emphasis on the importance of restrictions on the functions based on the user role that also protects the department records as well. If a Facilities user account is trying to add or modify an IT Department asset records, the system did not permit this action to continue; thus, keeping the latter asset records safe from any misclicks or accidents and vice versa as compared to their Excel files. In addition, the RAMS system was able to make sure that the required fields are not left empty by the user. In relation to this, the confirmation pages also help the user see all their inputs for each asset ID to make sure they input it correctly before saving into the database.

Aside from security, accuracy and efficiency are in a close tie; the RAMS was able to keep track of the assets and accurately produce the results when a user needs it. They did not have to comb through every row just to find the asset that they needed, and they did not have to copy paste the same details on each asset ID based on the quantity whenever they need to add it in the database records as compared to the MS Excel file of the company.

Lastly, usability is the lowest among the attributes of the system, but it is still deemed acceptable in the eyes of the testers. Unlike the Excel sheet where all information is displayed at once; thus, overwhelming the user, icons and proper labeling of buttons help them understand better in navigating through the RAMS system while performing their tasks.

On the other hand, the CES test results also did not have a perfect score of 7, but it did get within the good score range. The testers had a good experience in testing out the RAMS system; they were able to add, find, and edit the assets effortlessly without damaging the other records.

To conclude, the result shows a good sign that all testers can understand what they are doing in the RAMS system and do the necessary tasks with ease as compared to the cumbersome SM Excel sheets.

5 CONCLUSION

The researchers were able to make this Capstone successful with the use of the Agile methodology approach. Company A experienced challenges in tracking and managing their appliances, furnitures, and IT appliances by using MS Excel. Considering that this is a big project, the researchers divided it into smaller and manageable tasks while also being able to collaborate with the stakeholders for its business processes, progress, and improvement. The researchers were able to develop a web-based system that keeps track of the life cycle of the asset where every asset record is secured and protected. In the end, Company A were supplied with an asset management system that they considered useful, user-friendly, efficient, and functional based on the requirements and scope of this project.

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